

Survey showcases for synergy of wind lidar, cloud radar, and ceilometer

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Integrating Doppler Wind Lidar (DWL), Doppler Cloud Radar (DCR) and ceilometer data is essential for enhancing our understanding of atmospheric dynamics and for discerning wind characteristics that influence the formation and distribution of various atmospheric constituents.

Having several showcases in order to highlight the synergetic use of DWL, DCR and ceilometer datasets is also important because each instrument provides high-quality datasets in different atmospheric conditions. Also, the integration of these instrument datasets provides a more comprehensive understanding of various atmospheric phenomena, such as wind patterns, cloud dynamics, and aerosol distribution. The showcases consist in a one-month analysis of several parameters measured by DWL, DCR and ceilometer for three ACTRIS stations: RADO-Bucharest-Romania, Granada-Spain and Hyytiälä-Finland (Fig. 1). Each station provides distinct atmospheric characteristics due to their placement in diverse places around Europe. Also, all three stations provided continuous datasets of all variables of interest for the analysed period.

Fig. 1. Geographical locations of the stations providing datasets used in this study: Bucharest, Granada and Hyytiälä

Datasets used in this analysis are provided by Cloudnet Data Portal (<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/>) and are available free of charge (under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 international licence). For this study a one-month period of Target classification products along with DWL data was used (01.05.2023—31.05.2023). The Target Classification algorithm (Hogan and O'Connor, 2004) combines DCR and ceilometer data, along with microwave radiometer and profiles and Integrated Forecast System (IFS) data in order to provide a state-of-the-art typing method of the atmospheric constituents. The particles are separated into 11 distinct classes:

Class 0: Clear sky (not shown in the analysis)

Class 1: Cloud liquid droplets only

Class 2: Drizzle or rain

Class 3: Drizzle or rain coexisting with cloud liquid droplets

Class 4: Ice particles

Class 5: Ice coexisting with supercooled liquid droplets

Class 6: Melting ice particles

Class 7: Melting ice particles coexisting with cloud liquid droplets

Class 8: Aerosol particles, no cloud or precipitation

Class 9: Insects, no cloud or precipitation

Class 10: Aerosol coexisting with insects, no cloud or precipitation.

DWL datasets comprise continuous vertical measurements, along with VAD scanning scenarios (proposed by Päsche et al., 2015). Datasets are further used in a processing algorithm developed by Manninen et al., 2018 (Halo toolbox) to obtain wind characteristics.

Contoured frequency by altitude diagrams (CFADs) of Target classification and vertical doppler velocity along with hourly averaged horizontal wind field (horizontal wind speed and direction) are provided in this analysis in order to provide the distribution of various atmospheric constituents and wind behaviour over analyzed period. CFADs are provided up to 12 kilometres altitude (maximum altitude that wind lidar can perform measurements) while the hourly averaged wind speed and direction are performed to a maximum of 3 kilometres (the maximum altitude with a reliable SNR in the scanning scenarios—see Ortiz Amezcua et al., 2022; Pîrloagă et al., 2023)

All three instruments used in this study requires existence of atmospheric constituents in order to return the radiation back to the instrument, therefore, a CFAD of radar reflectivity was necessary to understand the distribution of these constituents with altitude in the atmosphere during the analysed period

This analysis can be performed on longer time periods, annually, seasonal or even on a multiyear period.

Showcase 1: RADO-Bucharest station

Fig. 1.1. CFAD of Target Classification at RADO-Bucharest station

Fig. 1.2. CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at RADO-Bucharest station

Fig. 1.3. Hourly horizontal wind speeds (left) and horizontal wind directions (right) from DWL at RADO-Bucharest station

Fig. 1.4. CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at RADO-Bucharest station

CFAD of Target Classification at RADO-Bucharest station (Fig. 1.1) presents a distinct pattern with classes 1, 4 and 5 reaching up to approximately 11 km altitude, class 8 reaching a maximum of approximately 5 km and all the rest of the classes (2, 3, 6, 7, 9 and 10) are displayed below 4 km altitude. Classes 1, 4 and 5 (*Cloud liquid droplets only, Ice particles and Ice coexisting with supercooled liquid droplets*) are main components of clouds (low, medium and high clouds) while classes 2, 3, 6, 7 (*Drizzle or rain, Drizzle or rain coexisting with cloud liquid droplets, Melting ice particles, Melting ice particles coexisting with cloud liquid droplets*) are related to phenomena that occur in the warm part of the atmosphere. Also, all classes related to ice (4, 5, 6, 7) start from 1 km altitude upwards. Thus, we can establish that in average, the brightness temperature for the analysed analyzed period occurs at approximately 1 km altitude for this location. Class 8 presents a distinct behaviour compared to all other classes-starts from minimum altitude and occurs up to 5,5 km altitude, this can be explained by convection that occurs during spring months (validated by Fig. 1.2 that shows strong vertical positive wind speeds in the 1-5 km altitude interval). Number of profiles for all classes on all altitudes are similar (<6000 profiles) except 5 peaks:

1. Class 2 under 2 kilometres altitude where a peak of approximately 10000 profiles occurs;
2. Class 9 in the 1-2 kilometres altitude interval where a peak of approximately 10000 profiles occurs;
3. Class 4 in the 2,5-10 kilometres altitude interval where a peak of approximately 20000 profiles occurs;
4. Class 8 below 3 kilometres where a peak of approximately 25000 profiles occurs;
5. Class 10 below 2 kilometres where a maximum of approximately >60000 profiles occurs;

CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at RADO-Bucharest station (Fig 1.2) presents a symmetry below 5 kilometres altitude illustrating both positive and negative vertical velocities. Small velocities (<5 m/s) can be seen up to 12 km altitude, this could explain the vertical air motions of mid and high clouds (thunderstorm clouds). Most of the profiles are displayed at very low speeds (<1 m/s) up to 3 kilometres altitude.

Hourly averaged horizontal wind speeds (Fig. 1.3-left) and horizontal wind directions (Fig. 1.3-right) from DWL at RADO-Bucharest station presents a typical spring wind pattern for this area (see Pîrloagă et al., 2023) with high wind speeds as altitude increases reaching a maximum of approximately 13 m/s while wind direction is predominantly from East and Northeast.

CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at RADO-Bucharest station (Fig. 1.4) shows a maximum reflectivity frequency in the -30--20 dBZ interval within 1 km altitude closest to the ground. Separate to this peak is another pattern of high reflectivity frequency decreasing with altitude from -30 dBZ at 10 km altitude to 15 dBZ at 3 km altitude. This behaviour is a typical for this location (see Pîrloagă et al., 2022)

Showcase 2: Granada station

Fig. 2.1. CFAD of Target Classification at Granada station

Fig. 2.2. CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at Granada station

Fig. 2.3. Hourly horizontal wind speeds (left) and horizontal wind directions (right) from DWL at Granada station

Fig. 2.4. CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at Granada station

CFAD of Target Classification at Granada station (Fig. 2.1) show a very similar pattern with Fig 1.1. Similar with RADO-Bucharest station CFAD, Classes 1,4,5 are rising up to approximately 12 km altitude, ice related classes (4, 5, 6 and 7) start from 1,5 km altitude (instead of 1 km as RADO-Bucharest) and class 8 occurs up to 5,5 km altitude. Similar with RADO-Bucharest there are 5 peaks of number of profiles: class 2 under 2 km altitude, class 4 in the 2,5-10 km altitude, class 8 under 3 km altitude, class 9 under 2,5 km altitude and class 10 with a maximum of 57000 profiles under 2 km altitude.

CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at Granada station (Fig. 2.2) show a similar pattern with Fig 1.2. The vertical velocity data shows a symmetry pattern (similar with RADO-Bucharest) with a more contoured data in the very high-speed area of the graph at approximately 20 m/s (positive and negative) for all altitudes.

Hourly averaged horizontal wind speeds (Fig. 2.3-left) and horizontal wind directions (Fig. 2.3-right) from DWL at Granada station presents a pattern with low speeds (<5 m/s) for all altitudes and all time intervals. Thus, a highly turbulent horizontal wind direction is presented.

CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at Granada station (Fig. 2.4) shows a similar pattern with Fig. 1.4 with a maximum reflectivity frequency in the -50—-30 dBZ interval within 2 km altitude closest to the ground. Separate to this peak is another pattern of high reflectivity frequency decreasing with altitude from -20 dBZ at 9 km altitude to 15 dBZ close to ground.

Showcase 3: Hyytiälä station

Fig. 3.1. CFADs of Target Classification at Hyytiälä station

Fig. 3.2. CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at Hyytiälä station

Fig. 3.3. Hourly horizontal wind speeds (left) and horizontal wind directions (right) from DWL at Hyttiälä station

Fig. 3.4. CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at Hyttiälä station

CFAD of Target Classification at Hyttiälä station (Fig. 3.1) show a similar pattern with Figures 1.1. and 2.1. Similar with RADO-Bucharest and Granada stations, Classes 1,4,5 are rising up to approximately 12 km altitude and class 8 occurs up to 5 km altitude. Ice related classes (4, 5, 6 and 7) start close to ground (instead of 1 km as RADO-Bucharest and 1.5 km as Granada) this shows that brightness temperature for this period is non-existent (temperatures close to the ground level are $<0^{\circ}\text{C}$). Similar with RADO-Bucharest and Granada there are 5 peaks of number of profiles: class 2 under 2 km altitude, class 4 in the 1-9 km altitude, class 8 under 3 km altitude with a maximum of 54000 profiles, class 9 under 2,5 km altitude and class 10 under 2 km altitude.

CFAD of vertical doppler velocity from DWL at Hyttiälä station (Fig. 3.2) show a similar pattern with Fig 1.2 and 2.2. The vertical velocity data shows a symmetry pattern (similar with RADO-Bucharest and Granada) with even more contoured data for all velocities and for all altitudes. Also, the

maximum around 0 m/s is in the lower part of the atmosphere than other two stations (<2 km altitude).

Hourly averaged horizontal wind speeds (Fig. 3.3-left) and horizontal wind directions (Fig. 3.3-right) from DWL at Hyytiälä station presents a pattern with low speeds (approximately 5 m/s) in the lower part of the atmosphere all time intervals and higher speeds as altitudes increases (similar with RADO-Bucharest). Horizontal wind direction is predominantly from the North.

Turbulent wind directions 1500 m altitude in Granada and Hyytiälä stations are present because the DWL data from these two stations (scanning scenario data) were filtered with the experimental processing algorithm by Cloudnet while RADO-Bucharest DWL scanning data were processed internally at station (thanks to Mariana Adam). Both methods use a version of processing algorithm developed by Manninen et al., 2018.

CFAD of radar reflectivity from DCR at Hyytiälä station (Fig. 3.4) shows a similar pattern with Fig. 1.4 and 2.4. Due to an artefact in DCR data, the peaks close to ground and below 9 km altitude downwards are not as clear as the other two stations. Also, this artefact was even more visible in the altitude bin closest to the ground and was eliminated from the data.

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